

**A STUDY ON COLLEGE STUDENTS FOOD
CONSUMPTION PATTERNS IN COIMBATORE**
Rithekaa Ravi Kumar*, Dr. V. B. Mathipurani, Dr. D. Divya
Prabha*** & S. Selva Krishna****

* PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor, PSG Institute of Advanced Studies, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

As the consumers are trying adapt with the dynamic environment and its technologies they have faced a lot of changes from their lifestyle to sleep patterns, most important including the type of food consumed. The food consumption patterns have changed drastically over this short period of time. Not only the adults, but also has a huge impact on all the age groups of the society mainly affecting the teenage and school going groups of children. A lot of junk food and other types have paved their way into the market and also have captured a huge market share. The conclusion is that the students are more aware about their food habits but a clear picture towards their pattern is missing which has to be rectified by self conscious towards their patterns which leads to a healthy life in future.

Key Words: Food habits, Adults & Patterns

Introduction:

As we are aware of the drastic changes in the food consumption patterns of all age groups from the healthy to the fit. And fast food has made a humongous impact on our society and has changed very much in a short period of time. Now to consider the college going students as they lack time for various things and they are loaded with work they don't have enough time to concentrate on themselves. Apart from that not all college canteens provide the students with a healthy menu. The students have also gotten so addicted to fast food that they have forgotten how healthy food even tastes. This has made them ready to even spend a great amount on junk food bringing their market shares high.

Literature Review:

Sam Abraham, Manuel Martinez, Gabriela Salas, Jessica Smith (2018): Explore college students' perceptions of the health effects of fast food consumption and their eating habits. The problem was explored in a quantitative survey using a cross sectional approach with a descriptive design.

Greyce Luci Bernardo, Manuela Mika Jomori, Ana Carolina Fernandes Rossana Pacheco Da Costa Proenca: To analyze the results of studies on the food intake of college students. The results demonstrates that most college students have an unhealthy eating behaviors, such as high intake of fast foods, sweets, soft drinks, and alcoholic beverages, and low intake of fruits, vegetables, fish, whole grains, and legumes. Undergraduate students of health sciences, such as nursing, nutrition, and medicine, did not have healthier diets too.

Sam Abraham, Manuel Martinez, Gabriela Salas, Jessica Smith (2018): The purpose of this study was to examine college students eating habits and knowledge of nutritional requirements for positive health. The students are knowledgeable that consuming fast food, soda, and processed food are unhealthy as they contain additives.

Francesco Bogarda (2013): The aim of this study was to assess the eating habits of a group of university students, to highlight any differences between students living at and away from home and to examine aspects of their health and nutritional status.

Mohsen Ebrahimi (2011): This study designed for understanding the nutrition knowledge, attitude and food habits of college's students. Results show that nutrition knowledge score in physical education student were highest and in business management student were lowest

Statement of the Problem:

The changing consumption basket can be examined in numerous ways. Firstly, at the varying weights that food items contrasted with non-food items have been occupying from time to time and secondly, within the food basket, the intensity of switch over from cereals to non-cereal items. The temporal profile of the consumption basket along the above lines would clearly signal the changing consumer tastes, choices and preferences over time, as the consumers move up on the per capital income ladder. Dietary diversification in rich income groups is causing another concern. Even at higher income level, where there is no economic constraint to consume more food, some population shows under nutrition and there is decline in the average level of energy intake. It was revealed that young and child population in rich households eat more junk food, spicy food, readymade sweets and they are developing distaste for healthy food and that has been taken as problem towards the study.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the changes in food consumption pattern among college students.
- To know about the use of following food consumption patterns among students.
- To analyze constraints in the consumption of food patterns among students.

Scope of the Study:

Consumption is an integral part of our life. It is present from the beginning to the end everywhere we go. We buy, eat, use and take advantages of different things. Of course, consumption itself is not a menace for our world but its patterns and effects. In the course of time, we become aware of the negative impact of our consumption patterns on the environment. This allows us to change and join the sustainable development approach. Consumer patterns change for both micro and macro reasons. The study will help the students maintain their health in future period of time.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: The research study applied here is purely descriptive.

Sampling Technique: The simple random sampling method was used for the primary data collection. Simple random sampling is the basic sampling technique where we select a group of subjects (a sample) for study from a larger group (a population). Each individual is chosen entirely by chance and each member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample. Every possible sample of a given size has the same chance of selection; i.e. each member of the population is equally to be chosen stage in the sampling process. There are two types of sampling techniques. They are Probability sampling and Non-Probability sampling. The researcher adopted Non- probability sampling.

Sample Size: 250 students are chosen as a sample size for the study.

Area of Study: Coimbatore

Data Collection:

- **Primary Data:** Information obtained from the original source by research is called Primary Data. They offer much greater accuracy and reliability. The data was collected from the respondents through the questionnaire.
- **Secondary Data:** In means data that are already available i.e., it refers to the data which have already been collected and analyzed by someone else. The data was collected from the websites and journals.

Tools Used for the Study: Percentage analysis, Rank correlation and Kruskal Wallis test.

Limitations of the Study:

- 150 respondents cannot represent the population, as a whole. So the findings may be biased.
- Time plays a havoc role in data collection. So, the sample is restricted to 150.
- The study area is limited to Coimbatore

Analysis and Interpretation:

Gender:

	Frequency	Percent
Male	123	49.2
Female	127	50.8
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about the gender of the respondents were out of 250 respondents 49.2% are male and 50.8% are female.

Educational Qualification:

	Frequency	Percent
Graduate	233	93.2
Post Graduate	17	6.8
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about educational qualification of the respondents were out of 250 respondents 93.2% are graduates and 6.8% are post graduates.

Type of Family:

	Frequency	Percent
Nuclear	149	59.6
Joint	101	40.4
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about type of family of the respondents were out of 250 respondents 59.6% are from nuclear family and 40.4% are from joint family.

Level of Awareness about Food Consumption Patterns:

	Frequency	Percent
Low	5	2

Average	169	67.6
High	61	24.4
Very High	15	6
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about level of awareness about food consumption patterns. Out of 250 respondents 2% said they have a low level of awareness towards food consumption patterns, 67.6% said they have average awareness, 24.4% said that they have high awareness and 6% said that they have very high awareness.

Source of Getting Awareness about Food Consumption Patterns:

	Frequency	Percent
T.V	39	15.6
Magazines	61	24.4
Friends and Relatives	144	57.6
News Papers	6	2.4
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about source of getting awareness about food consumption patterns. Out of 250 respondents 15.6% are getting awareness about food consumption patterns through televisions, 24.4% are getting awareness through magazines, 57.6% are getting through friends and relatives and only 2.4% are getting awareness through news papers.

Person Taking Decision Regarding Food Consumption Patterns:

	Frequency	Percent
Self	132	52.8
Spouse	109	43.6
Parents	4	1.6
Children	5	2
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about person taking decision regarding food consumption patterns. Out of 250 respondents 52.8% are taking their own decision towards purchasing food consumption patterns, 43.6% are taking their spouse decision in to consideration, 1.6% obey with their parents decision and 2% obey with their children decision.

Level of Acceptance towards Benefits of Food Consumption Patterns for Health:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	249	99.6
Neutral	1	0.4
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about level of acceptance towards benefits of food consumption patterns for health. Out of 250 respondents 99.6% strongly agree and 0.4% are neutral.

Level of Acceptance towards Benefits of Food Consumption Patterns for Environment:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	223	89.2
Agree	26	10.4
Neutral	1	0.4
Total	250	100

Interpretation: The above table shows about level of acceptance towards benefits of food consumption patterns for environment. Out of 250 respondents 89.2% strongly agree, 10.4% agree and 0.4% are neutral.

Rank Correlation for Factors Related to Motives of Food Consumption Patterns:

Particulars	X	Y	R1	R2	D	D ²
Concern for health	140	21	1	3	-2	4
Concern for status	34	127	3	1	2	4
Concern the environment	10	93	4	2	2	4
Betterment of living style	76	9	2	4	-2	4
						16
N=4					1-R	0.4
					R	0.6

Interpretation: The above table shows about the correlation of the ranks given based on motives towards food consumption patterns. The correlation for the ranks given is at 0.6. it shows that the ranks given are moderately

correlated. The first rank was given to concern for health which reveals that the health consciousness is the motive for food consumption patterns by the respondents.

Comparison between Gender and Acceptance and Satisfaction towards Food Consumption Patterns:

	Gender	N	Mean Rank
Acceptance towards purpose of food consumption patterns	Male	123	118.15
	Female	127	132.61
	Total	250	
Acceptance towards consumption of food consumption patterns	Male	123	127.06
	Female	127	123.99
	Total	250	
Acceptance towards challenges of food consumption patterns	Male	123	114.33
	Female	127	136.32
	Total	250	
Satisfaction towards food consumption patterns	Male	123	116.28
	Female	127	134.43
	Total	250	

Test Statistics ^{a, b}				
	Acceptance towards purpose of food consumption patterns	Acceptance towards consumption of food consumption patterns	Acceptance towards challenges of food consumption patterns	Satisfaction towards food consumption patterns
Chi-Square	2.694	0.117	6.639	4.31
df	1	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	0.101	0.733	0.01	0.038
a. Kruskal wallis test				
b. Grouping Variable: Gender				

Interpretation: The above table shows that there is no relationship between gender and Acceptance towards purpose of food consumption patterns (0.101), Acceptance towards consumption of food consumption patterns (0.733) as the level of significance is greater than 0.05. There is a relationship between gender and acceptance towards challenges of food consumption patterns (0.010) and Satisfaction towards food consumption patterns (0.038) as the level of significance is lesser than 0.05.

Findings:

- Most of the respondents are female.
- Maximum of the respondents are graduates.
- Most of the respondents are from nuclear family.
- Maximum of the respondents have average awareness towards food consumption patterns.
- Majority of the respondents are getting awareness about food consumption patterns through their friends and relatives.
- Majority of the respondents are taking their own decision towards purchasing food consumption patterns.
- Majority of the respondents strongly agree towards benefits of food consumption patterns for health.
- Majority of the respondents strongly agree towards benefits of food consumption patterns for environment.
- Health consciousness is the motive for food consumption patterns by the respondents.
- There is a relationship between gender and acceptance towards challenges of food consumption patterns and Satisfaction towards food consumption patterns.

Suggestions:

Individual consumers need to be more aware and educated about their individual dietary needs, and devise their dietary strategies for food choice according to their health. In this context, the supportive role of families, teachers, and governments in making individuals, especially the younger generation, more educated about health and nutrition can make a significant difference in the improvement of community health worldwide.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that the students are more aware about their food habits but a clear picture towards their pattern is missing which has to be rectified by self conscious towards their patterns which leads to a healthy life in future.

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